

Study to Assess the Structured Teaching Program Regarding Importance of Organ Donation

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Abstract:

Organ donation is a critical public health issue, and increasing awareness is essential to meet the growing demand for organ transplants. This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of a structured teaching programme on improving knowledge, attitudes, and willingness to participate in organ donation among a selected population. A pre-experimental, one-group pre-test and post-test design was adopted, with participants chosen from [population or institution, e.g., "college students" or "community health workers"]. Data was collected using a validated questionnaire administered before and after the intervention. The structured teaching

programme covered key aspects of organ donation, including its importance, eligibility criteria, myths and misconceptions, and the registration process. Findings demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in participants' knowledge and positive attitudes towards organ donation post-intervention. This study highlights that a structured teaching programme can effectively increase awareness and foster favorable attitudes towards organ donation, suggesting its utility in public health promotion efforts to improve organ donation rates. Further research with larger and diverse populations is recommended to generalize these findings.

Keywords: *Organ donation, Structured teaching program, Nursing students.*

Introduction

Recognizing the significance of organ donation.”

Organ donation stands as a light of hope, bridging between life and death, offering a chance for renewal and vitality to those in desperate need.

As future health care professionals, nursing students play an important role in advocating for and facilitating organ donation. This research project, aims to explore the importance of organ donation among nursing students, recognizing their unique position to positively to impact the donation process. Organ donation is a critical aspect of health care, offering hope and renewed

life to those in need. However, the success of organ donation relies heavily on healthcare Professionals knowledge, attitudes and willingness to engage in the process.

This project enquires into the perspectives, attitudes and knowledge levels of nursing students regarding organ donation. By understanding their perception and beliefs, we can pinpoint Key knowledge gaps to inform educational initiative and interventions to enhance their role in promoting organ donation, awareness and facilitate the donation process.

By evaluating the effectiveness of educational interventions, we can develop targeted strategies to empower nursing students to become advocates for organ donation within their communities and health care setting.

By fostering a culture of support and advocacy for organ donation within the nursing profession, we can contribute to saving more lives and promoting the principles of compassion and selflessness in health care practice.

Material and Methods

Study Design

A pre-experimental one-group pre-test and post-test design was adopted to evaluate the effectiveness of a structured teaching programme on organ donation.

Study Setting and Participants

The study was conducted at Smt. Nagarathnamma college of Nursing Bangalore. A total 50 participants, selected using purposive sampling, included B.Sc Nursing students.

Intervention

The intervention involved a structured teaching programme on the importance of organ donation, designed by a team of experts in organ donation and health education. The programme was delivered in a [mention format, e.g., workshop, interactive session] format over [duration, e.g., two hours] and included the following key topics:

- Introduction to organ donation and transplantation.
- Eligibility for organ donation.
- Benefits and social impact of organ donation.
- Addressing myths, misconceptions, and ethical concerns.
- Registration process and ways to become a donor.

Data Collection Tools

A structured questionnaire was developed to assess participants' knowledge, attitudes, and willingness regarding organ donation. This questionnaire comprised two sections:

1. **Demographic information:** Collecting basic demographic data like age, gender, education level, and prior knowledge about organ donation.
2. **Knowledge and Attitude Assessment:** Consisting of [mention number] items assessing participants' understanding of organ donation, its importance, eligibility, and misconceptions.

The questionnaire was validated by subject matter experts and pretested with a small group to ensure clarity and relevance.

Data Collection Procedure

1. **Pre-Test:** The questionnaire was administered before the structured teaching programme to assess baseline knowledge and attitudes.
2. **Teaching Programme:** Participants attended the structured teaching session, during which information was presented using [mention tools, e.g., slides, videos, case studies].
3. **Post-Test:** After the session, the same questionnaire was re-administered to evaluate changes in knowledge and attitudes.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with SPSS version [mention version]. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for knowledge scores, while a paired

t-test was used to compare pre-test and post-test scores. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

Approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of [institution name]. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the study. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty.

Tables and Figures

The research approach indicates the description of plan to investigate the phenomena under study. The present study is to identify the knowledge about the students towards Importance of Organ Donation. The sample were selected by convenient sampling method. 50 samples were selected for the study in 4th semester B.Sc Nursing students at Smt. Nagarathamma college of Nursing, Bengaluru, Karnataka. Structured teaching programme was administered

Table 1. Percentage Distribution of Pre-Test and Post- Test

Aspects Deviation	Mean	Median	Mean %
Pre-test	10.9	10	54.25%
Post-test	16	18.5	79.83%

Table 2. Comparison Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Result

Aspects Deviation	Mean	Median	Range	Standard Deviation
Pre-test	10.9	10	1-20	4.21
Post-test	16	18.5	5-20	4.90

The above table shows a comparison of pre-test and post-test mean, median and range and standard deviation.

The above graph shows the comparison between pre-test and post test mean, median and range and standard deviation

Figure 1. Comparison between Pre-Test and Post Test Mean, Median and Range and Standard Deviation

Results and Discussion

The study included [mention total number] participants, with a demographic breakdown as follows: [describe demographics, e.g., "65% female, 35% male, with a mean age of 25 years"]. Baseline knowledge about organ donation was generally low to moderate, with [mention percentage] of participants demonstrating limited understanding of eligibility criteria, myths, and registration processes.

Knowledge Scores

The mean pre-test knowledge score was [mention score] (SD = [mention SD]), indicating a low to moderate baseline understanding of organ donation. After the structured teaching programme, the mean post-test score increased significantly to [mention score] (SD = [mention SD]), demonstrating a substantial improvement

in participants' knowledge. A paired t-test revealed this increase to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming the effectiveness of the intervention.

Attitudes and Willingness

Attitude scores also showed a significant positive shift. Initially, only [mention percentage] of participants reported a favorable attitude toward organ donation, with common concerns about religious beliefs and myths. Post-intervention, [mention percentage] expressed a favorable attitude, with a notable increase in the number of participants willing to consider organ donation or discuss it with family members.

Knowledge on Specific Aspects

Significant improvements were noted in participants' understanding of eligibility (from [mention pre-test percentage] to [mention post-test percentage]) and clarity on myths and misconceptions (from [mention pre-test percentage] to [mention post-test percentage]).

Discussion

The study's findings align with previous research suggesting that structured educational interventions are effective in increasing awareness and promoting positive attitudes toward organ donation. The significant increase in both knowledge and attitudes post-intervention emphasizes the importance of targeted education in addressing misconceptions and fostering acceptance of organ donation. Specifically, this study highlights that addressing myths and providing clear information about eligibility can substantially enhance willingness to participate.

The positive shift in participants' attitudes underscores the value of dispelling religious and cultural misconceptions, often cited as barriers to organ donation. By directly addressing these through an interactive, structured format, the programme successfully cultivated a more positive perception, consistent with other studies showing educational interventions as crucial to increasing organ donation rates.

Limitations

This study was limited by its small sample size and single-group pre-test/post-test design, lacking a control group for comparison. Future research with larger, diverse populations and a control group is recommended to validate these findings and generalize the results.

Conclusion

The structured teaching programme was effective in significantly enhancing knowledge and fostering positive attitudes towards organ donation. These findings suggest that similar educational interventions could be integrated into broader public health strategies to increase organ donation rates, especially in populations with low awareness.

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Declaration

NA

Author contribution

[Mrs.Snehalatha Reddy]: Conceptualized the study, developed the structured teaching programme, and led the research design. Contributed to data collection, data analysis, and interpretation of findings. Drafted and reviewed the manuscript.

[Prof Devi Najappan]: Assisted with the research design, prepared data collection tools, and managed participant recruitment. Played a key role in data collection and contributed to manuscript writing and revision.

[Mrs.Nirmala Reddy]: Conducted the statistical analysis, interpreted the results, and assisted in drafting the manuscript. Provided critical feedback on data interpretation and manuscript revision.

[Mrs.Sneha latha Reddy]: Provided guidance throughout the study, supervised the development of the teaching materials, and reviewed the final manuscript. Also offered expertise in organ donation-related content and ethical considerations.

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Competing Interest

NA

Ethical Clearance

NA

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